

Quality of The Problem Lesson, Its Goals and Objectives

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Abstract:

This article outlines the issues of introducing innovative approaches to improving learning processes. There are also recommendations for the development of high pedagogical technologies.

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Introduction

Today it is considered recognized that the optimal planning and regulation of innovation activities in the republic should be based on a scientifically based forecast of the relevant areas of science, technology, national economy and public education.

This view is expressed in the relevant guidance documents. Prognostic studies of innovation are important for the development and regulation of the country's economy, for the effective implementation of the scientific, technical and technological revolution. However, the ratio of plans and forecasts is not so simple, and to clarify it one needs to see not only the links, but also the differences between planning and forecasting. The plan gives us a project of the future, based on our understanding of the possibilities of its implementation and the needs for it. The forecast is intended to give an objective picture of the future, based on a scientific analysis of the natural historical process of the development of society.

The plan expresses today's view of the development goals of the relevant area and the means and implementation. The forecast must take into account possible changes in both the goals themselves and the means available to achieve them. Therefore, there may be contradictions between plans and forecasts, the consideration of which is very important for scientific forecasting. This is especially important for such a rapidly developing and changing area as small business and scientific and technical information. The forecast should reflect not only today's ideas about the organization and methods of functioning of systems and innovation activities, but also those changes (development) in this area that are almost imperceptible today.

The problems of state regulation of innovation activity in fact turn out to be broader than it follows only from the practice of scientific information activity. These problems are closely related to the general phenomenon of information in society (the whole world), the functioning of various information services necessary for the development of the national economy and cultural construction.

Therefore, it is so relevant today that it is broad, designed for the prospect of posing informatics problems for the development of innovative activity.

A serious one, in our opinion, is a judgment about the future development of innovation activity, based on the analysis of the principal difficulties that forecasters have encountered today. It is on the basis of this analysis of difficulties and contradictions that the methodology of scientific forecasting and regulation of innovative activity in the republic should be built. In relation to the triad-based prediction methodology, one can presumably speak of its following structure:

- identification of an invariant (fundamental) goal;
- identification of obstacles to its achievement;
- finding ways to overcome these obstacles.

The forecast of development and regulation of innovation activity should ultimately be based on indicating the ways that will allow to overcome existing and emerging obstacles to the harmonious development of scientific and technical information, ensuring the achievement of the fundamental goals of the innovation project. These paths are not so diverse, and therefore the emerging forecast scenarios differ mainly in what resources can be attracted for a radical improvement and development of the republic's innovation activity. Of course, one of the important sources of information on ways to solve problems of development and regulation

of innovation activity is familiarization of foreign experience, which revealed that automated data banks connected to network structures providing remote access for consumers should become the basis of promising information systems.

Essential importance is the fact that today in the organization and regulation of innovation activities, an increasing role is played by programs (or, in other words, targeted integrated programs). Innovative activities (projects) should focus not only on various areas of science and industry, but also on the current structure of government programs.

The future themes of innovative projects will be to a large extent problem-oriented. To envisage the necessary composition of this network is basically the task of the central sectoral and inter-sectoral territorial scientific and technical information. From the point of view of the organization, this means the need to involve these bodies in making forecasts for the development of sectoral territorial innovation projects. However, there is still no uniform methodology for making forecasts on sectoral and territorial issues on innovation activity. Existing industry forecasts are difficult to integrate into a single system. In any case, there is no uniform methodology for forecasting the development and regulation of innovation activities in the Republic. It seems to us that as a principle basis of such a technique one can choose a scheme according to which the forecast is carried out by analyzing ways to overcome difficulties in achieving the fundamental goal. To formulate this goal, it is necessary to consider prognostic research from the point of view of its national economic significance.

We are interested in the goal of development and regulation of the innovation activity of the Republic, which, as follows from what has been said, consists in increasing the number of people involved in an innovation project at a socially necessary level. If this goal becomes conscious, then it thereby acquires a regulative nature, which allows it to rely on it in the

compilation of long-term forecasts. It is in this case that the forecast of development and regulation of innovation activity can be based on the fact that maximum efforts will be made (within the limits of potential resources) to expand the contingent of consumers, who are provided with the socially necessary level of awareness.

It should be emphasized that the level of development of any science is characterized by its ability to make reasonable predictions of the phenomena under study. This shows a special place of prognostic studies in the development and regulation of innovation activities. They are based on the scientific results achieved and prove to be the level of these results. Meanwhile, the forecast research in the field of regulation of innovation activity is an integral part of the state program. The point is that the structure of the forecast of innovative activity should flow not from the established tradition, not from today's capabilities, but should necessarily be derived from the fundamental properties of the posed problem of the national economy, public education, etc. But in order for this conclusion to be able to really influence the development and regulation of the system by the innovative activity of the republic, it must be quite widely understood. Then the understanding of the necessary structure of innovation activity can influence the setting of specific goals and problems and thus be embodied in specific state plans.

Without this, the development and regulation of innovation can get a distorted character that does not correspond to the true interest of the national economy and public education. The lack of a clear understanding of the fundamental goals and criteria makes forecasting impossible, because the future is then much more uncertain. Therefore, forecasting the development and regulation of innovation activity throughout the Republic turns out to be important organizational and methodological issues that should take their rightful place. This

is a prerequisite for the success of work on forecasting the development and regulation of innovation activities.

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1

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